

COGNITIVE BIASES IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP: UNDERSTANDING THE DETERMINING ROLE OF DEMOGRAPHICS AND FIRM CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract

This study aims to examine whether the cognitive biases - optimism, overconfidence, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution differ across Bangladeshi Small and Medium Sized Enterprises (SMEs) based on demographics and firm-specific characteristics. . Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire from 354 SME entrepreneurs across four purposively selected cities: Dhaka, Khulna, Rajshahi, and Jashore, achieving a 97.52% response rate. Convenience sampling was used to choose individual SME owners. Since the data in this study had a non-normal distribution and demographic and the firm-related variables were categorical, non-parametric statistical tests were used to address the research objective. Cognitive biases across several categories of SME entrepreneurs were compared using the Kruskal-Wallis H and Mann-Whitney U tests. The findings reveal that the cognitive biases among SME entrepreneurs significantly vary across both demographic and firm characteristics. Specifically, optimism is associated with education level, source of ownership, location, and business sector. Overconfidence significantly relates to age, source of ownership, location, and business sector. The illusion of control is influenced by an entrepreneur's age, experience, and firm location. At the same time, the tendency to make self-serving attributions is linked to factors like education, ownership, age, location, and the size of the business. Notably firm age does not have a significant effect on any cognitive bias. These findings highlight the heterogeneous nature of cognitive biases among SME entrepreneurs and call for tailored interventions that address both individual and firm-level factors to improve decision-making.

Keywords: Cognitive biases, Entrepreneurs, SMEs, Demographics, Bangladesh

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurs make substantial contributions to the building up of economies around the world as they play an essential role in the establishment and growth of Small and

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Medium Enterprises (SMEs). SMEs are the building blocks of most economies, accounting for about 50% of jobs worldwide and 90% of enterprises (World Bank, n.d.). According to the European Investment Bank, 99% of all enterprises and nearly two-thirds of all jobs in the EU are provided by SMEs. Up to 40% of GDP in emerging economies is generated by formal SMEs, and the percentage grows dramatically if informal SMEs are taken into account. According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics' 2013 Economic Census, there were over 7.8 million SME firms in Bangladesh, engaging about 25 million people. It indicates the crucial role played by SMEs in the country's economic landscape. As of 2024, these enterprises represented around 25% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), thus being an important driver of the economy.

Entrepreneurs adopt their unique decision-making approaches in volatile and uncertain contexts. They often depend on heuristics and cognitive shortcuts to speed up decision-making. Since the works by Busenitz & Barney (1997) and Baron (1998), the study of entrepreneurs' biases has gained momentum in entrepreneurial decision-making research. After the COVID-19 epidemic recently, possibly permanently, altered the socioeconomic landscape of the world, entrepreneurs were required to take quick, important, and creative decisions in order to survive (Kurdoglu et al., 2022). They frequently apply simplifying decision-making techniques. These swift and immediate decisions are often misled by numerous cognitive biases. Biases such as overconfidence, optimism, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution can influence entrepreneurs' risk perception, opportunity evaluation (Keh et al., 2002), and strategic decision-making (Afroze & Rashid, 2025 Douglas, 2009). Due to bias, entrepreneurs are tempted to engage in risky behavior, resulting in irrational decision-making that could compromise the performance of an organization. On the flip side, these biases may cultivate in entrepreneurs a sense of motivation, optimism, and dedication while facing setbacks. This happens as the result of changes in entrepreneurs' cognition over time; for example, variables like gender may influence rationality and entrepreneurial conduct (Bendell et al., 2020).

Seminal works by Busenitz and Barney (1997) and Baron (1998) initiated the study of entrepreneurial biases, identifying traits like overconfidence and optimism as influential in decision-making. Subsequent research, such as Forbes (2005), linked overconfidence to entrepreneurs' age and founder status. He concluded that founder-CEOs tend to exhibit higher overconfidence bias than non-founders. Both demographic factors (Dubey & Sahu, 2022), such as age, education, and experience, and firm-specific factors, such as the organization's size or age, have a major effect on entrepreneurial behavior (Capolupo et al., 2024). Research indicates that the aforementioned variables affect the degree and prevalence of cognitive biases in entrepreneurs. For example, prior experience and industry dynamics strengthen the adverse effects of optimism on entrepreneurial business performance (Hmieleski & Baron, 2009). Shepherd et al. (2015) have highlighted that the occurrence of biases mainly depends on personal experience, an entrepreneur's social network, and personal capital. The acquired knowledge of experience, although generating important lessons and skills, can also exacerbate cognitive biases like overconfidence. Experienced entrepreneurs, particularly those with previous successes, can build a heavy reliance on heuristics, assuming they have a unique capability to alter outcomes in uncertain

contexts (Ucbasaran et al., 2009). This can be explained by several conditions: geographic context, like cultural factors, and institutional factors, such as SME size and age. These institutional factors play a more significant role in shaping the relationship between biases and entrepreneurial decision-making (Capolupo et al., 2024).

Despite these contributions, we found several critical gaps in the literature. First, much of the existing literature is geographically concentrated in North America and Europe. Those research provides a Western-centric understanding of entrepreneurial cognition. The unique socio-cultural and institutional contexts of emerging economies, such as Bangladesh, remain underexplored. Zhang and Cueto (2017) have emphasized the importance of studying entrepreneurial biases in diverse economic environments. Second, previous studies have largely examined one or two demographic variables (e.g., gender or age) or a single firm characteristic at a time. Such a fragmented approach has limited our understanding of how a combination of factors influences biases. Additionally, few studies have analyzed firm-specific factors affecting cognitive biases. While Capolupo et al. (2024) have recently acknowledged the role of institutional and firm characteristics, empirical evidence remains limited.

The present study seeks to address these gaps by examining how both demographic (age, gender, education, prior experience) and firm characteristics (size, age, industry, ownership type) relate to cognitive biases among SME entrepreneurs in Bangladesh. This research aims to assess multiple cognitive biases: optimism, overconfidence, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution bias. This study provides a more holistic understanding of how these psychological factors vary across different entrepreneur and firm profiles. The study's findings will contribute to scholarly understanding of cognitive biases in under-researched settings. Thus, the research question seeks to answer whether cognitive biases differ by various demographic and firm characteristics of entrepreneurs. And to answer this question, this study aims to:

- 1) Explore variations in cognitive biases across different demographic groups of entrepreneurs of the SME sector; and
- 2) Identify differences in cognitive biases across firm characteristics within entrepreneurs of the SME sector.

The structure of this paper is as follows: The literature review on cognitive biases in SMEs is covered in Section 2, and a description of the methodologies is given in Section 3. The study findings are reported in Section 4, and the key findings are presented in Section 5. and conclusion with future research directions is discussed in Section 6.

2. Literature review

Cognitive biases such as optimism, overconfidence, the illusion of control, and self-serving attributions have a significant impact on entrepreneurial decision-making. Individual background traits can shape how a person views events, affecting how they make decisions and their choices (Hambrick, 2007). These biases are often caused by the inherent uncertainty and complexity of entrepreneurial environments, and they are influenced by demographic factors such as age, education, experience, and gender, as

well as firm-level attributes such as size, age, and ownership structure.

An anticipation of favorable outcomes, or optimism, is influenced by institutional and personal factors. In a similar way, optimistic novice entrepreneurs often overestimate their chances of success in comparison to more seasoned ones (Cassar, 2009). Considering the fact that optimism lowers with entrepreneurial experience, experienced entrepreneurs are less sensitive to optimism bias (Fraser & Greene, 2006). Higher education also enhances optimism by raising self-confidence in their ability to make decisions (S. Chen et al., 2013; Landier & Thesmar, 2009). Founding entrepreneurs who begin their own businesses are likely to be more optimistic (Landier & Thesmar, 2009), since they often overstate the business's growth potential and downplay its risks.

Overconfidence, defined as an inflated assessment of one's capabilities or influence over results, is a common cognitive bias. Because of their expertise and information-seeking patterns, elder entrepreneurs prefer to take a more cautious approach, while younger entrepreneurs tend to be overconfident (Forbes, 2005). Male entrepreneurs exhibit greater overconfidence than their female counterparts. These differences may be due to cultural expectations and gender norms (Koellinger et al., 2013). Experience affects overconfidence in complex ways; nascent entrepreneurs often overrate their abilities, while successful experiences may strengthen overconfidence by incorrectly attributing success to personal skill instead of outside factors (Hayward et al., 2006; Koellinger et al., 2007). Overconfidence can be affected by firm-level attributes such as firm size (Singh, 2020). Additionally, entrepreneurs with external funding display lower degrees of overconfidence because their actions are monitored, and investors hold them responsible for their choices (Forbes, 2005). Entrepreneurs who are overconfident might take risks and grasp possibilities, but if left uncontrolled, this can result in costly mistakes.

The illusion of control, where entrepreneurs overestimate their ability to influence outcomes that are not controllable and dependent on external factors beyond their control, is particularly common in entrepreneurial settings. According to a conceptual paper, this bias is more noticeable among entrepreneurs of smaller and younger firms. Because in their businesses, they often take on multidimensional roles and attribute successes to one's own skills rather than external factors (Simon & Houghton, 2002). The illusion of control is influenced by optimism and overconfidence (Koellinger et al., 2007). Thus, determinants of those biases may also affect the illusion of control. Experienced entrepreneurs are also susceptible to this bias, as past decision-making successes may lead to an overgeneralized sense of control (Shepherd, 2003).

People have a general tendency to attribute positive outcomes to their personal skills and blame external factors for failures. This is known as self-serving attributions that are influenced by demographic and firm characteristics. Self-serving attribution bias is related to optimism (Hayward et al., 2006) and overconfidence (Moosa & Ramiah, 2017). When optimistic entrepreneurs experience success, they are likely to attribute it to their skills and hard work. This tendency reinforces their positive self-image, and experienced entrepreneurs are more likely to reveal this bias, as they attribute favorable outcomes to their leadership and decision-making (Hayward et al., 2006). At the firm level, founders of smaller or founder-managed firms exhibit stronger self-serving

tendencies as they perceive themselves as central to their firm's success.

Thus, the proposed hypotheses are:

H_{1a}: Entrepreneur's optimism bias differs across each group of demographic factors.

H_{1b}: Entrepreneur's optimism bias differs across each group of firm-specific factors

H_{2a}: Entrepreneur's overconfidence bias differs across each group of demographic factors.

H_{2b}: Entrepreneur's overconfidence bias differs across each group of firm-specific factors.

H_{3a}: Entrepreneur's illusion of control bias differs across each group of demographic factors.

H_{3b}: Entrepreneur's illusion of control bias differs across each group of firm-specific factors.

H_{4a}: Entrepreneur's self-serving attribution bias differs across each group of demographic factors.

H_{4b}: Entrepreneur's self-serving attribution bias differs across each group of firm-specific factors.

3. Methods

3.1 Sample and data collection

The target population of this research includes small and medium-sized enterprise owners within the formal economy of Bangladesh. According to the SME Foundation (2022), there were approximately 7.81 million small and medium establishments in Bangladesh. Overall, entrepreneurs in the sample were selected in line with specified selection criteria; they were working in the formal sector of the economy, owned their businesses, had a minimum of six employees, and engaged in the agriculture and/or manufacturing sectors. This study did not include entrepreneurs involved in the service sector. In the first step of sample selection, four cities of Bangladesh—Dhaka, Khulna, Rajshahi, and Jashore—were chosen purposefully as the research areas. At a later stage, individual entrepreneurs were selected by using a convenience sampling technique. The data was collected from primary sources, that is, SME entrepreneurs, by using a structured questionnaire through the face-to-face interview method. Interviewing entrepreneurs ensures a high response rate and accurate interpretation. A total of 363 interviews were conducted, out of which 354 were usable. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first part of it consists of questions related to the socio-demographic information of individual entrepreneurs, and the second part contains Likert scale items for measuring entrepreneurs' cognitive bias status. Data on the type of industry, number of employees, age of business, and ownership type were under the business profile section. Entrepreneurs' profiles included name, gender, age, years of experience, and years of education.

3.2 Measurement instruments

To assess overoptimism, we took measurements on scales used by Wally & Baum

(1994) and Simon et al. (1999). A sample item is “I usually expect improvement in my life.” High scores indicate overoptimism, and low scores indicate an absence of optimism.

Overconfidence refers to the overestimation of one’s abilities, knowledge, or judgment in decision-making contexts. Five items were adapted from Ahmad et al. (2021) and Mouna & Jarboui (2015). Sample items include: *“It is unquestionable that my ability is better than others in making strategic decisions.”* and *“I feel certain that the investment will turn out well, and definitely I have the ability to manage it.”*

Illusion of Control: Illusion of Control refers to when individuals overestimate their ability to influence outcomes that are largely determined by external factors or chance. This measure was developed by Langer & Roth (1975) and also used by Houghton et al. (2000). The respondents’ illusion of control was measured using the five items. *For example, “As I have experience predicting market demand in other business sectors not related to my current business, I would become more accurate in predicting the total demand for my existing business.”* and *“The strategies I choose would be the major determinant of the success of my business.”*

Self-Serving Attribution (SSA) is a cognitive bias in which individuals attribute their successes to internal factors, such as their abilities, effort, or skills, while blaming external factors, such as luck or unfavorable circumstances, for their failures. This bias helps individuals maintain a positive self-image and protect their self-esteem. This scale was developed using items like *“If I got a good return, then the reason that I attribute to this is as my sufficient effort or right strategy.”*

3.3 Data analysis technique

Descriptive statistical studies illustrate the attributes of the respondents' socio-demographics and their business features. These studies provided a comprehensive insight into SME entrepreneurs in Bangladesh. Descriptive of optimism, overconfidence, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution bias were also presented to have a general understanding of entrepreneurs’ cognitive bias status.

This study employs non-parametric statistical tests to answer the research question: whether cognitive biases vary across different demographic and firm-specific characteristics of SME entrepreneurs. The choice of non-parametric methods was based on several considerations. First, demographic and firm characteristics, which are categorical in nature, are more appropriate for non-parametric methods. Second, normality tests (Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov) indicated non-normal data distributions. So, the application of a parametric test is not permissible. And third, non-parametric tests are robust to skewed distributions in subgroup comparisons and ensure the reliability of results. Given these considerations, Kruskal-Wallis H and Mann-Whitney U tests were used to compare cognitive biases across different groups of SME entrepreneurs. The Kruskal-Wallis H test is suitable for comparing cognitive biases across three or more independent groups. It was used to analyze differences in cognitive biases across educational attainment (secondary, bachelor, master’s, and above), source of ownership (founder, inherited, bought from others), age categories (21–35 years, 36–50 years, 51 and above), experience levels (low, medium, high), firm size (measured by employee number) (1–30, 31–60, 61 and above), and location of the

business (Dhaka, Khulna, Rajshahi, Jashore), and firm age categories (1–10 years, 11–20 years, 21 and above).

The test produces a chi-squared test statistic (H) and an associated p -value to determine whether differences exist across groups. If the p -value is below 0.05, it indicates that there is a significant difference in cognitive bias levels across groups. The Mann-Whitney U test was applied when comparing cognitive biases across two independent groups. This test was specifically used to examine differences in biases between business sectors, manufacturing vs. agriculture. A statistically significant Z-score ($p < 0.05$) indicates that one group has significantly higher or lower bias levels than the other.

4. Results

4.1 Demographic and firm-specific characteristics

Table 1 depicts the demographic insights of entrepreneurs and their firm characteristics. It is evident that just above 50% of entrepreneurs fall within the 36–50-year age group, followed by the older group (51 and above) at 26.8%, and the relatively younger group represents only 20.6%. It indicates that middle-aged entrepreneurs dominate the entrepreneurial landscape. Regarding the source of ownership, nearly two-thirds of the entrepreneurs founded their own businesses. It indicates a strong inclination toward self-initiated ventures. A smaller proportion of entrepreneurs got the ownership from their parents, and ownership through purchase is only 8.8%, indicating that generational or acquired businesses are less common in this sample. In terms of educational qualification, many entrepreneurs possess secondary education as their highest in number in our sample, with fewer having attained a bachelor's or master's degree. It reflects the fact that having higher education is not a precondition for being an entrepreneur. In terms of experience, more than half of the entrepreneurs have relatively low experience, which ranged from one to fifteen years. A significant portion has mid-level experience ranging from sixteen to thirty years, while only a small minority has entrepreneurial careers for over three decades. This indicates that entrepreneurship is an attractive career path for individuals at various stages of their professional journey.

The study sample comprises firms from the manufacturing sector and the agricultural sector. 63.8% of the firms employ 1–30 people, 23.2% of the firms have 31–60 employees, and 13% have more than 61 employees. This distribution indicates that this landscape is dominated by small-scale operations. Firm age distribution reveals a mix of new and established businesses. Regarding firm longevity, our sample includes a balanced mix of new and established businesses. Firms, those operating for less than a decade, form the largest group, while businesses with over two decades of experience also maintain a strong presence. Dhaka is the main hub of entrepreneurial activity. Other regions, such as Jashore, Khulna, and Rajshahi, also contribute to the entrepreneurial landscape, but to a lesser extent.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

Entrepreneurs' Attribute	Category	Percentage
Age	21–35 Years	20.6

	36-50 Years	52.5
	51 and above	26.8
Source of Ownership	Founder	72.9
	Inherited	18.4
	Bought from others	8.8
Education	Secondary	42.9
	Bachelor	29.9
	Master's & above	27.1
Experience	Low (1-15 years)	54.0
	Medium (16-30 years)	36.7
	High (31 and above)	9.3
Firm Profile	Category	Percentage
Business Sector	Manufacturing	79.4
	Agriculture	20.6
Number of Employees	1-30	63.8
	31-60	23.2
	61 and above	13.0
Firm Age	1-10 Years	40.1
	11-20 Years	33.3
	21 Years and above	26.6
Location	Dhaka	37.3
	Khulna	20.9
	Rajshahi	18.6
	Jashore	23.2

Source: Survey data

4.2 Cognitive biases

Table 2 represents the mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis of each bias, namely optimism, overconfidence, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution. The mean values for the biases indicate a general tendency towards high scores on a five-point Likert scale. Self-serving attribution has the highest mean score, 4.107. It means entrepreneurs strongly attribute successes to their abilities while avoiding the responsibility of failures. The second highest mean score is 4.043 for illusion of control, indicating that respondents tend to overestimate their ability to influence outcomes even if it is not within their control. Overconfidence also scores relatively high, reflecting a strong belief in one's abilities. Optimism has a mean score of 3.799, which is still substantial despite being the lowest among all four biases. It indicates

that entrepreneurs are positive in expecting better outcomes. Standard deviation shows the variation of entrepreneurial cognitive biases. Here, optimism has the highest variation while self-serving attribution bias exhibits the lowest deviation across the sample. The biases are negatively skewed, meaning that entrepreneurs have a general tendency towards the higher end of the scale, i.e., they are inclined to bias. Here, the illusion of control has the highest skewness value, and overconfidence has the highest kurtosis value. This table 2 assists as a foundational basis to reveal if demographic and firm characteristics influence these biases.

Table 2: Summary statistics for cognitive biases

Cognitive Biases	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Optimism	354	3.7994	.72128	-.912	1.129
Overconfidence	354	3.9953	.60813	-1.004	2.354
Illusion of control	354	4.0431	.58191	-1.189	1.773
Self-serving attribution	354	4.1069	.50680	-.4570	.0430

4.3 Optimism bias across demographic and firm-specific characteristics

Kruskal-Wallis test and Mann-Whitney test results show that the entrepreneur's optimism bias differs across each category of education and source of ownership of entrepreneurs' demographic characteristics (Table 3). For different levels of education, optimism differs, and this result is significant with a chi-squared value of 8.576 ($df = 2$, $p = 0.014$). The mean rank of optimism bias for higher education is greater than that of secondary and bachelor levels of education. It reflects that higher education enhances optimism among entrepreneurs. Our result is also significant with the source of ownership (Chi-Square = 8.159, $df = 2$, $p = 0.017$), where founders belong to the highest optimism score (mean rank = 186.85). The hypothesis (H1a) is partially supported as optimism bias differs across each category of education and source of ownership, but not for age group and experience group.

The test results related to H1b show mixed results; the entrepreneur's optimism bias differs across each group of location and business sector (Table 4). In contrast, the difference based on the number of employees (firm size) and firm age is not supported by our test results. Geographic location was also a significant factor (Chi-Square = 13.82, $df = 3$, $p = 0.003$), with entrepreneurs in Khulna showing the highest optimism (mean rank = 214.05). The Mann-Whitney U test is used to identify the industry-wise differences. To evaluate the difference between the manufacturing sector (Median=4.00, N=281) and the agricultural sector (Median=4.33, N=73), entrepreneurs show a significant difference in optimism bias ($U = 8019.00$, $Z = -2.910$, $p = 0.004$, $r = .155$).

Table 3: Optimism bias across demographic characteristics

Category	Groups of each category	N	Mean Rank	Test statistic	df	Asym p. Sig.
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Kruskal-Wallis test results						
Education	Secondary	152	161.36	8.576*	2	0.014
	Bachelor	106	180.65			
	Master's and above	96	199.58			
Source of ownership	Founder	258	186.85	8.159*	2	0.017
	Inherited	65	151.88			
	Bought from others	31	153.39			
Age	21-35 years	73	178.29	2.500	2	0.287
	36-50 years	186	170.49			
	51 and above	95	190.61			
Experience	Low	191	182.65	1.179	2	0.555
	Medium	130	170.2			
	High	33	176.42			

Table 4: Optimism bias across firm-specific characteristics

Category	Groups of each category	N	Mean Rank	Test statistic	df	Asym p. Sig.
Kruskal-Wallis test results						
Employee number	1-30	226	170.59	3.339	2	0.188
	31-60	82	185.41			
	61 and above	46	197.36			
Location	Dhaka	132	170.67	13.82**	3	0.003
	Khulna	74	214.05			
	Rajshahi	66	176.15			
	Jashore	82	156.6			
Firm age	1-10 years	142	187.81	2.566	2	0.277
	11-20 years	118	172.51			
	21 and above	94	168.19			
Mann-Whitney U test						
			Mann-Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-	Effect size

				tailed)/	
Business sector	Manufacturing	281	8019.00	-	0.004
	Agriculture	73		2.910**	.155

4.4 Overconfidence bias across demographic and firm-specific characteristics

From Table 5, we can see that the source of ownership and age significantly influence overconfidence bias. On the other hand, education and experience do not significantly influence overconfidence; hence, hypothesis H2a is partially supported. For the source of ownership, the test yielded a Chi-Square value of 11.103 ($df = 2, p = 0.004$). Like the case of optimism, founders show the highest overconfidence (mean rank = 187.84), followed by those who inherited (mean rank = 156.98) and purchased their businesses (mean rank = 134.44). This suggests that entrepreneurs who initiate, create, and run their ventures are high in confidence. Age also significantly impacts overconfidence (Chi-Square = 8.725, $df = 2, p = 0.013$), with older entrepreneurs (51 and above) exhibiting the highest overconfidence (mean rank = 196.50).

Hypothesis H2b provides mixed support. From Table 6, we can see that location and business sector significantly influence overconfidence bias. But education, experience, number of employees, and firm age did not show significant differences. Location shows a significant effect on overconfidence (Chi-Square = 11.337, $df = 3, p = 0.010$), with entrepreneurs in Jashore demonstrating the highest overconfidence (mean rank = 195.82). The Mann-Whitney U test is used to identify the business sector-wise differences. To evaluate the difference between the manufacturing sector (Median=4.00, N=281) and the agricultural sector (Median=4.33, N=73), entrepreneurs show a significant difference in optimism bias ($U=7694.500, Z=-3.344, p=.001, r=.178$).

Table 5: Overconfidence bias across demographic characteristics

Category	Groups of each category	N	Mean Rank	Test statistic	df	Asym p. Sig.
Kruskal-Wallis test results						
Education	Secondary	152	176.3	0.592	2	0.744
	Bachelor	106	173.39			
	Masters and above	96	183.94			
Source of ownership	Founder	258	187.84	11.103**	2	0.004
	Inherited	65	156.98			
	Bought from others	31	134.44			
Age	21-35 years	73	150.32	8.725*	2	0.013
	36-50 years	186	178.46			
	51 and above	95	196.5			

Experience	Low	191	166.52	5.091	2	0.078
	Medium	130	191.94			
	High	33	184.14			

Table 6: Overconfidence bias across firm-specific characteristics

Category	Groups of each category	N	Mean Rank	Test statistic	df	Asymp. Sig.
Kruskal-Wallis test results						
Employee number	1-30	226	171.08	2.546	2	0.280
	31-60	82	189.29			
	61 and above	46	188.01			
Location	Dhaka	132	184.88	11.337*	3	0.010
	Khulna	74	175.03			
	Rajshahi	66	142.75			
	Jashore	82	195.82			
Firm age	1-10 years	142	170.63	4.064	2	0.131
	11-20 years	118	192.72			
	21 and above	94	168.77			
Mann-Whitney U test						
Business sector	Manufacturing	281	7694.500	-3.344**	.001	.178
	Agriculture	73				

4.5 Illusion of control bias across demographic and firm-specific characteristics

H3a showed partial support (Table 7), with differences in age and experience categories significantly affecting the illusion of control bias, but not education or source of ownership. For age, the test results show a Chi-Square value of 12.457 ($df = 2$, $p = 0.002$), with entrepreneurs aged 51 years and above showing the highest illusion of control (mean rank = 206.61). Experience also gives a significant impact (Chi-Square = 7.116, $df = 2$, $p = 0.028$), where entrepreneurs with a high experience category (31+ years) exhibit the strongest illusion of control (mean rank = 216.09).

The results from Table 8 show that location significantly affects the illusion of control (Chi-Square = 9.336, $df = 3$, $p = 0.025$). On the other hand, the illusion of control does not vary by number of employees, firm age, or business sector. Thus, H3b was supported for one but not others, offering mixed support.

Table 7: Illusion of Control Bias across Demographic Characteristics

Category	Groups of each category	N	Mean Rank	Test statistic	df	Asym p. Sig.
Kruskal-Wallis test results						
Education	Secondary	152	169.25	3.413	2	0.181
	Bachelor	106	192.33			
	Masters and above	96	174.19			
Source of ownership	Founder	258	183.28	5.397	2	0.067
	Inherited	65	172.65			
	Bought from others	31	139.53			
Age	21-35 years	73	154.05	12.457**	2	0.002
	36-50 years	186	171.84			
	51 and above	95	206.61			
Experience	Low	191	167.33	7.116*	2	0.028
	Medium	130	182.64			
	High	33	216.09			

Table 8: Illusion of Control Bias across Firm-Specific Characteristics

Category	Groups of each category	N	Mean Rank	Test statistic	df	Asymp. Sig.
Kruskal-Wallis test results						
Employee number	1-30	226	175.54	0.343	2	0.842
	31-60	82	183.14			
	61 and above	46	177.09			
Location	Dhaka	132	186.1	9.336*	3	0.025
	Khulna	74	189.46			
	Rajshahi	66	143.99			
	Jashore	82	179.84			
Firm age	1-10 years	142	167	2.854	2	0.240
	11-20 years	118	187.81			
	21 and above	94	180.43			
Mann-Whitney U test result						
			Mann-Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)/	Effect size

Business sector	Manufacturing	281	9122.500	-1.478	.140	.078
	Agriculture	73				

4.6 Self-serving attribution bias across demographic and firm-specific characteristics

The results from nonparametric tests (H4a) indicate that education, source of ownership, and age significantly impact self-serving attribution bias, not supported for experience (Table 9). Thus, the hypotheses for these variables are accepted. For education, the test detects a Chi-Square value of 9.879 ($df = 2$, $p = 0.007$), with entrepreneurs holding secondary education showing the highest self-serving attribution (mean rank = 192.96). Source of ownership with founders exhibits the highest self-serving attribution (mean rank = 189.88) and yields a significant effect (Chi-Square = 17.937, $df = 2$, $p = 0.000$). Age significantly impacts self-serving attribution (Chi-Square = 7.180, $df = 2$, $p = 0.028$). It means older entrepreneurs (51 and above) are more biased (mean rank = 192.72) in comparison to other groups.

H4b was supported in part. The results from nonparametric tests show that the number of employees and location significantly impact self-serving attribution bias, whereas firm age did not (Table 10). The number of employees also significantly affects self-serving attribution (Chi-Square = 10.226, $df = 2$, $p = 0.006$), with smaller firms (1–30 employees) displaying the highest bias (mean rank = 189.35). Location is another significant factor (Chi-Square = 52.704, $df = 3$, $p = 0.000$).

Table 9: Self-serving attribution bias across demographic characteristics

Category	Groups of each category	N	Mean Rank	Test statistic	df	Asym p. Sig.
Kruskal-Wallis test results						
Education	Secondary	152	192.96	9.879**	2	0.007
	Bachelor	106	179.07			
	Masters and above	96	151.29			
Source of ownership	Founder	258	189.88	17.937**	2	0.000
	Inherited	65	158.4			
	Bought from others	31	114.52			
Age	21-35 years	73	151	7.180*	2	0.028
	36-50 years	186	180.13			
	51 and above	95	192.72			
Experience	Low	191	169.95	3.150	2	0.207
	Medium	130	182.6			
	High	33	201.14			

Table 10: Self-serving attribution bias across firm-specific characteristics

Category	Groups of each category	N	Mean Rank	Test statistic	df	Asymp. Sig.
Kruskal-Wallis test results						
Employee number	1-30	226	189.35	10.226**	2	0.006
	31-60	82	165.54			
	61 and above	46	140.59			
Location	Dhaka	132	184.13	52.704**	3	0.000
	Khulna	74	138.7			
	Rajshahi	66	132.82			
	Jashore	82	237.8			
Firm age	1-10 years	142	168.51	1.910	2	0.385
	11-20 years	118	185.09			
	21 and above	94	181.55			
Mann-Whitney U test						
			Mann-Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)/	Effect size
Business sector	Manufacturing	281	9042.00	-1.566	.117	.083
	Agriculture	73				

5. Discussion

This study investigates whether the cognitive biases vary across SME entrepreneurs based on firm-specific characteristics and owners' demographics. For this purpose, four biases, namely optimism, overconfidence, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution, were taken. Across all tested hypotheses (H1a–H4b), the findings reveal a pattern of mixed results. While certain demographic and firm-specific factors exhibited significant associations with the cognitive biases (optimism bias, overconfidence, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution bias), other factors did not.

The results (H1a and H1b) find a significant relationship between optimism and education, source of ownership, location, and business sector. Entrepreneurs with higher educational qualifications exhibit greater optimism. It can be explained in a way that education helps to build self-efficacy, a key driver of optimism. Self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1997) explains that belief in one's own ability positively impacts estimation of success. Founders are more optimistic as compared to entrepreneurs who inherit or purchase businesses. It reflects their emotional attachment and faith in their targets (Cardon et al., 2012). Entrepreneurs use heuristics to identify opportunities and show higher optimism compared to managers (Busenitz & Barney, 1997). The findings on differences in the business sector show the higher optimism observed among

entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector. The increasing global demand for food and agricultural products due to population growth and rising standards of living may enhance optimism among agricultural entrepreneurs.

Based on the significance level, the results reveal that the source of ownership, age, and business sector are influencing factors for entrepreneurial overconfidence (H2a and H2b). Founders exhibit higher overconfidence as they are directly involved in the decision-making process (Chen et al., 2022; Hayward et al., 2006). This bias can be useful in the early stages of entrepreneurship, as it drives persistence, which ultimately leads to increasing their confidence in decision-making (Chowka, 2023). Entrepreneurs inheriting or purchasing businesses usually operate within established frameworks. As such, they are less likely to be involved in high-risk actions and consequently exhibit less bias. Founders often surrounded themselves with like-minded people. These people validate their idea by reinforcing entrepreneurs' confirmation bias. This technique is useful in motivation, but it limits the boundary of criticism and increases overconfidence in making decisions (Busenitz & Barney, 1997). Entrepreneurs inheriting or purchasing businesses usually establish settings and teams, which may provide a more balanced perspective. The test result shows that the relationship between age groups is positive. It can be explained in a way that accumulated experience and past successes reinforce self-belief (Hayward et al., 2006). Thus, older entrepreneurs exhibit a greater level of overconfidence. Entrepreneurs in the agriculture sector have a high level of overconfidence. Business sector-wise differences may be due to differences in risk-taking and confidence through perceived market stability (Baron, 2000). These results agree with the findings from hubris theory, which identifies overconfidence as a key driver of entrepreneurial risk-taking (Hayward et al., 2006).

Age, experience, and geographical location significantly influence the illusion of control in entrepreneurs (H3a and H3b). Older and more experienced entrepreneurs often feel they have greater control due to their continued decision-making roles (Langer, 1975). As they experienced over time, they relied on established heuristics. Thus, experienced entrepreneurs differ from novices in evaluating opportunities (Baron & Ensley, 2006). As they acquire knowledge and skills, their self-perception shifts. These changes may impact how they recognize and assess new opportunities, which can influence their motivation to continue or quit their ventures (Abebe et al., 2020; Shepherd & Patzelt, 2018). It may also raise confidence in their ability to control such factors, which are outside their control, in unpredictable scenarios. This happens because their prior successes reinforce their belief in their decision-making (Hayward et al., 2006). This "success breeds confidence" cycle continues and magnifies the illusion of control. In contrast, the illusion of control did show significant differences across Dhaka, Khulna, Rajshahi, and Jashore (H3b). These findings are consistent with entrepreneurial cognition literature (Hmieleski & Baron, 2009) which emphasizes that entrepreneurial thinking is shaped by the interaction between individual characteristics and environmental contexts.

Self-serving attribution is influenced by education, source of ownership, age, and firm size (H4a and H4b). Entrepreneurs, especially founders, give credit for successes to their abilities and blame external factors for failure. This tendency is due to their emotional attachment and operational involvement in the business (Pierce et al., 2001).

Entrepreneurs in smaller firms also show stronger self-serving tendencies. It may be because of their direct involvement in operating their business, while those in larger firms may attribute achievements to team efforts or systems. Higher education moderates this bias by supporting reflective decision-making and self-awareness (Schraw & Dennison, 1994). Older entrepreneurs exhibiting stronger biases, which indicate age, also play a significant role. The reason may be accumulated confidence through skill and experience over time. These results emphasize the role of personal and contextual factors in shaping attribution styles.

The results indicate that all four cognitive biases — optimism, overconfidence, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution — vary significantly across the four geographic locations (Dhaka, Khulna, Rajshahi, and Jashore). This suggests that the regional context plays an important role in shaping entrepreneurial cognition.

In summary (H1a-H4b) we see that location is the only firm characteristic that is common for all cognitive biases. Optimism, overconfidence, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution vary significantly across the four geographic locations (Dhaka, Khulna, Rajshahi, and Jashore). In different regions, entrepreneurs may experience distinct economic conditions, market dynamics, social norms, and levels of institutional support. These factors influence how they perceive opportunities, risks, and control. As such, bias differs geographically. Additionally, we see that firm age does not have a significant effect on any cognitive bias. This reflects that the duration of business operations has a minimal effect on entrepreneurs' cognition. This finding aligns with research suggesting that biases are more influenced by personal characteristics, such as emotional involvement and individual experience (Ucbasaran et al., 2009). Similarly, experience is the only factor significant for the illusion of control, but not for other biases.

6. Conclusion and future research direction

We present in this paper a thorough investigation of how optimism, overconfidence, illusion of control, and self-serving attribution bias vary across demographic and firm-specific traits among SMEs in Bangladesh. The findings reveal that entrepreneurs exhibit different levels of cognitive biases. Bias can vary based on factors like education, age, experience, ownership, size of the company, industry, and region. The results reveal that founders demonstrate higher levels of optimism, overconfidence, and self-serving attribution in comparison to those who inherited or purchased businesses. So, the psychological impact of direct involvement in business creation should be an important factor in deciding to be an entrepreneur. Additionally, older and more experienced entrepreneurs possess a high illusion of control. These findings could be beneficial to policymakers and entrepreneurship educators. We suggest the need for targeted training programs, and context-sensitive policies that consider both personal and firm-level factors to support more balanced and informed entrepreneurial decision-making. In this study, we focus on the relationship between cognitive biases and demographic and firm-specific factors. This study lays the groundwork for future investigations into causal relationships. Further research can be conducted on if there is any causal relationship between cognitive biases and performance outcomes, including sustainability, innovation, and profitability. Today's entrepreneurs live in a time of digital platforms and readily available AI-powered decision-making tools. It

might be beneficial to look into how technology reduces cognitive biases in entrepreneurial decision-making.

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